

Supplementary Material

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Figure S1: Biomass accumulation rate of fast- and slow-growing sugarcane internodes.

Figure S2: Linear regression of dry weight against internode length for two growth phases. Panels (A) and (B) represent different growth conditions (Fast Growth and Slow Growth). Dotted lines indicate regression fits for early growth (0-150 GDD) and mature phase (150-360 GDD), with corresponding R^2 values displayed above each fit. Significance levels: *** ($p < 0.001$), ** ($p < 0.01$), * ($p < 0.05$), n.s. (not significant).

Figure S3: Frequency distributions of transcription factor (TF) Proteins and their families. (A) Depicts the frequency of individual protein names, where the count for each TF is determined by its occurrence in the dataset. (B) The distribution of TF families, with frequencies indicating the number of occurrences for each family group.

Figure S4: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) plots of transcription factor protein expression profiles under different experimental conditions. (A) PCA colored by Condition, representing experimental treatment groups. (B) PCA colored by Age, highlighting expression changes across developmental stages. (C) PCA colored by Stage, showing distinct clustering of growth phases. Confidence ellipses indicate 95% confidence intervals, illustrating the variance within each group.

Figure S6: Connectivity distribution of proteins in the Trait-networks for glucan (A), xylan(B), sucrose (C) and lignin (D). Each panel shows a histogram of the proportion of connections per transcription factor (TF) , representing the number of TFS with a given level of connectivity, and a line graph which depicts the cumulative distribution of connectivity. "Only direct associations based on filtering for significance are shown. Colour indicates strength and direction of correlation."